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Combining the flipped classroom and simulation games in engineering education: a methodological survey

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, there has been a considerable shift in the way engineering education is approached, with increased demands for active learning and methodologies that emphasize soft skills, such as ability to communicate effectively, identify and solve problems, and function on multidisciplinary teams.

Within this scope, two methods have particularly been of interest in recent years: the flipped classroom and simulation learning. Ample evidence exists pertaining to the efficiency of the flipped classroom methodology. Similarly, extended state-of-the-art review suggests that proper application of simulation games in engineering education has the potential to maximize the learning outcome and transferability of academic knowledge to the industry. However, combining the flipped classroom with other active learning methodologies is a more recent development which has huge potential.

This paper aims at examining to what extent simulations and the flipped classroom can be used in conjunction to support students' motivation, engagement and learning outcomes. It will present findings based on a scoping review of research incorporating both methods. This review highlights how combination of simulation and the flipped classroom ranks higher than either of these methods alone. It makes an argument towards the use of meaningful gamification to enhance this combined model towards a more efficient holistic learning experience.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The flipped classroom

An increased interest has arisen lately in active learning in higher education, to ensure students' engagement and autonomy in learning, as well as learning outcomes which also incorporate 21st century soft skills [1]. Bishop and Verleger define the FC as "...an educational technique that consists of two parts: interactive group learning activities inside the classroom, and direct computer-based individual instruction outside the classroom" [2]. Although early experimentation in the FC was made in secondary education in the United States [3], it became quickly a staple of higher education. Flipping the classroom meant an opportunity to transform the usually heavily theoretical first undergraduate years into active learning, accelerating the transformation from surface learning to active learning in students [4]. There is ample literature pertaining to the efficient use of the FC in science education (e.g. [5]), and the diversity of research reviews of FC in the past ten years initiatives reveals the interest for the method in the scientific and educational discourse [2].

1.2 Simulation in engineering education

Within the field of active learning in engineering education, simulations have also become the object of increased focus. We will define simulations as "an interactive representation of reality based on the construction of a model of a system of which we want to understand the working" [6]. Landriscina argues that simulation potentially constitutes a suitable instructional method, in which learning requires a restructuring of the students' individual mental models through interactions between the individual mental model and the simulation one [6]. Although Landriscina establishes a clear separation between simulation and simulation games, he also underlines that both frequently overlap by having specific rules, goals and scores. Similarly, Deshpande and Huang through an extended state-of-the-art review suggest that proper application of simulation games in engineering education has the potential to maximize the learning outcome and transferability of academic knowledge to the industry [7]. Therefore, although simulation and simulation games present some differences in terms of scope and agency given to the learner, due to the fact that research into these methods have shown interest both for simulation and simulation games, we consider both to be of interest for this investigation.

1.3 Combining simulation and the FC

Although both the FC and simulations have been of greater interest in the discourse regarding higher education, research into combining the two appears to be still at an early stage. Previous research in combining the FC with active learning methodologies such as problem-based learning has been successfully carried out (e.g. [8], [9]). However, it appears that there is a lack of research and reviews in combining other methods, such as the FC and simulation, and a need to identify the conditions of its implementation, technology used, and learning outcomes. The aim of this paper is to investigate the literature regarding the combined use of the FC and simulation in engineering and science education. In order to perform this study, we will review the

literature using a scoping review method, to illustrate which research has been carried out in that field, and where research is still lacking on these subjects.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this paper, we have used Arksey and O'Malley's methodology [10], as expanded by Levac et al. [11]. The scoping review method uses the stages presented in the following sections.

2.1 Stage 1: identifying the research question

The focus of this research is to identify the circumstances under which the FC and simulation were used successfully in conjunction with each other or in the same course, and how both methodologies could be improved by being used in combination. To frame our investigation of the topic, we focused on the following research questions:

1. Which technologies and type of simulations were used for the implementation of simulations in the FC?
2. What were the educational outcomes of the use of simulations in the FC?
3. What is known of the conceptual framework used to incorporate simulations and the FC in engineering education?

2.2 Stage 2: identifying relevant studies

Arksey and O'Malley [10] suggest that a wide definition for search terms should be used. In light of the fact that some simulations are presented as simulation games [6], and that sometimes simulations are developed under a gamified environment, a large scoping review was done including all potentially relevant forms of game-based learning. The following research string was thus devised:

("game-based" OR "gamification" OR "serious games" OR "educational games" OR "simulation") AND ("flipped classroom")

The selection was then narrowed to select only articles explicitly pertaining to simulation, and then only to articles dealing with simulation in engineering education. The selected databases for this study were Scopus, Proquest, Web of Science, JSTOR and Google Scholar. Only peer-reviewed articles and papers, accessible in English, and in the period 2009-2019 (which coincides with the exponential development of the FC) were researched.

2.3 Stage 3: Study selection

Using the key search descriptors, 1356 articles were identified. After excluding duplicates, and articles studying active learning methodologies separately (FC or simulation separately and not in combination with each other), 70 articles were selected. These articles presented the combined use of the FC with either a simulation, a simulation game, or an educational approach relying on simulation such as the use of online virtual laboratories in the pre-class preparation phase. A further 34 articles focused on simulation in the FC, of which, after exclusion of study levels (elementary and high school) and subjects not relevant to this study (such as foreign

language education and teacher training), a final 24 articles were selected, which focused in simulation in engineering education. Studies were excluded on the following motives: research that did not fully take place in the FC, or that focused exclusively on simulation in the learning process, theoretical papers and reviews, and papers that did not include an evaluation in class.

2.4 Stage 4: Charting the data

The data extracted from the selection of articles was mapped using the following criteria: Study ID, Title, Journal/Publication, Author, Year, Country of study, Technology employed, Category of gaming elements employed, Position in the FC, Study level, Subject studied, Size of class, Learning outcomes, Evaluated variables and study focus, Study methodology, Theoretical framework for the study.

2.5 Stage 5: Collating, summarizing and reporting the results

The final stage of the scoping review summarizes and reports findings.

3 FINDINGS

A final selection of 24 articles was made, representing 12 different countries. Although the last decade was studied, the oldest study is only from 2013, and 20 out of 24 articles were published in the past three years only (2017-2019). The majority of these articles concerned the field of computer science and engineering (7 articles) followed by engineering technologies (6 articles), applied sciences (5 articles), and chemical and electrical engineering (2 each).

3.1 Which technologies were used for the implementation of simulations of the FC?

A minority of four articles offered an examination of simulations used in the pre-class process of the FC. Three out of four offered simulations in conjunction with instructional videos and other learning material ([12], [13], [14]), whereas the last one [15] used game-based learning as a means of preparation through a programming simulation. Four articles ([16], [17], [18], [19]) offered a simulation experience that encompassed the whole of the FC experience, all of them by using simulation in conjunction with gamification to support the whole structure of the FC. However, most articles used simulation during the in-class time, and the objective of the FC is to allow students to prepare efficiently for class, usually through instructional videos. 16 articles in total reference this approach.

There is, however, no way of asserting if one type of simulation was more frequently used. Deshpande and Huang [7] establish three different types of simulation: drill-based, exercise-based, and problem-based. Drill-based scenarios, in which we include access to a virtual lab or VR, allow student to practise specific manipulations in the reproduction of the real environment, or to observe a specific phenomenon or process ([5], [20]-[26]). Exercise-based simulation focus on students finding the correct technique to solve a problem. Simulations included in pre-class preparation fall under this category ([12]-[17], [27]). Problem-based simulations offer complex

scenarios, which allow students to explore multiple solutions and devise their own. They can take the form of mini-cases or project-based activities, including game production and design ([14], [18], [19], [28]-[31]). There is also no consistency in the technologies employed, which can include web-based simulation ([21], [27]), AR [22], simulation games ([15], [26]), machine simulators [24] or project-based simulation ([18], [19], [31]). The focus therefore seems to have been essentially in using the FC as a way to further the efficiency of the in-class simulation, allowing for extended tutoring time and face-to-face interactions.

3.2 Which were the educational outcomes of the use of simulations in the FC?

Three forms of evaluation and educational outcomes is observed in the selected articles. In 15 of the reviewed articles, the research investigated the students' performances, either through their grades, the pass rate of the class, or their knowledge in pre- and post-tests. 18 articles investigated the students' perception of the learning process, through their self-reported opinion of the efficiency of the method or interest in the studied subject. Finally, a minority of seven articles investigated more closely the student's living experience in the classroom by testing for motivation, stress level, engagement or cognitive load. More than half of the articles (13 out of 24) investigated two of these issues or more, three articles investigating all three of these aspects. All articles reported positive outcomes following the combination of the FC and simulation. Many articles report higher grades or higher pass rates in the classrooms, which used a combination of FC and simulation or a gamified environment ([16], [17], [22], [24], [26], [27], [30]), increased student satisfaction and interest ([5], [13], [14], [16], [21], [24], [27], [28], [30], [31]), and, when evaluated, improvement in students autonomy ([15], [16]), engagement and positive response to the class ([5], [16], [18], [28], [29], [32]). When evaluated against a different form of instructions, the combination of the FC and simulation yielded better learning outcomes than traditional lecture-based learning ([17], [22], [27]), non-flipped simulation [5], or traditional FC without simulation or gamified system ([12], [15], [18], [27]), both in terms of academic results and students' appreciation.

It should be noted however that few articles presented clearly limitation or negative outcomes to combining the FC and simulation. Two articles noted only a low and non-significant increase of interest [33], or understanding [23] in students. Similarly, only one study investigated the long-term impact on students' knowledge retention by doing a delayed post-test evaluation [22], this time with improved results in the three learning dimensions of knowledge, comprehension, and application.

3.3 What is known of the conceptual framework used to incorporate simulations and the FC in engineering education?

We finally investigated the theoretical background and theoretical framework to the selection of articles at our disposal. The majority of articles, 18 out of 24, referenced recent research in the FC. Six articles used the theoretical framework of research into gamification and game-based learning, and seven articles referenced research in

technology-enhanced learning or e-learning. However, only a minority of articles did use cognitive theories in their research, looking for example into self-regulated learning [28], self-efficacy [27], deep learning and cognitive load theory [5], adaptive learning [12], and constructivist theory [32]. Only one article presented a specific theoretical model [29], in the form of the Activity-Oriented Teaching Strategy (AOTS), a structure which integrates in its development both the FC, project role-play for developing project artefacts, teaching by example, and student seminars. Moreover, some articles presented little in terms of theoretical background or conceptual framework ([14], [25], [26]).

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Technology used in combining the FC and simulation

The articles presented in this scoping review show a wide variety of subjects and approaches to combining the FC and simulations, generally to positive outcomes. One study [20] insists on the high potential for combining the FC and simulation, as the former yielded more satisfying results than simulation alone. Our scoping review also identified the lack of specific focus on the post-class process, and in tools used to support the self-reflection on the learning process in students. Although a majority of articles, 18 of them, involve some measurements of the students' self-perception of the methodology, only four articles present focus on the whole of the FC process, especially by developing an online system meant to support students' engagement with the learning material, and appropriate use of gamification elements ([16]-[19]). There is therefore future potential into pursuing the use of simulation in the FC, and expanding upon it through a more holistic approach that would take into account the whole of the FC process, and through the development of tools that would facilitate the students' self-learning process.

4.2 Educational outcomes in combining FC and simulations

The scoping review shows positive results in terms of grade improvement and students' self-reported perceptions. However, the review showed that investigation into the learning experience itself was still limited. Few articles investigated students' motivation, engagement or attitudes towards the subject or towards learning. The result of the scoping review suggests that there is a significant gap in investigating students' motivation and engagement in the FC. Research into gamification in the FC offer many examples of such studies [34], which could easily be extended to the integration of simulation in the FC, or integration of simulation in a gamified FC. Finally, this scoping review also identified a significant gap into investigating the impact of the FC on students of different genders and economic situations. A single article [12] did a focus group on non-white non-male students and reported a more beneficial impact on female students and working students. In a context where the integration of more diverse populations of students represents a major challenge in higher education, specific investigation into the diversity of student populations still seems to be lacking.

4.3 Conceptual framework for the FC

The scoping review shows that the research into the conceptual framework to integrate fully the FC and simulations appears to be still lacking. A single article [29] offered an original theoretical model, and many articles did not offer a satisfying theoretical background. This lack of theoretical models for combining the FC and other active learning methodologies may explain the lack of interest given to the post-class learning process: as such, the FC experience still appears to be implemented in a disjointed fashion, with little continuity between the pre-class and the in-class periods, and even more so between the in-class and the post-class process. There is therefore potential both in developing more complete theoretical models for combining the FC and simulation, and in investigating its impact on students' motivation, aptitude for soft skills, and cognitive flexibility.

5 CONCLUSION

The FC may very well be one of the most emblematic efforts to overhaul traditional lecture-based learning in the 21st century. As efficiency of the FC is now thoroughly documented, the potential of combining the FC with other methodologies such as simulations is now starting to be documented. This review shows that the potential of such combination has been explored with success, with studies showing that the method was generally well-accepted by students, and resulted in higher engagement and more successful learning outcomes. Furthermore, the field still seems open to a variety of extended investigations: the impact of different forms of simulation, improvement in students' self-directed learning, and the learning outcome among students of different background, for example, should be explored in greater depth. The studies we investigated still approached the FC and simulations as separate methodologies, with the former facilitating the implementation of the latter. It must be expected that further development into combining active learning methodologies will result in greater incorporation, with the development of fully holistic educational model, relying on greater technological integration and improved use of data analytics tools.

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